

IN MEMORIAM
DAN CONSTANTIN JIPA
(1935-2020)

Berca, Vulcanii Noroiosi, Summer of 2019. Photo courtesy of Silviu Radan, Ph.D.

Dan Constantin Jipa, a great friend, an eminent, brilliant scientist, who has completely dedicated his life to Earth Sciences, passed away on September 28, 2020. Adieu dear friend! He worked with total dedication for over 60 years and his enthusiasm and interest in the profession did not fade even at the last moment - two months earlier, he was in the Bucegi Mountains where he had resumed his study of the Bucegi Conglomerates. We were good friends, we worked together and we supported each other to the best of our ability.

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Dan Jipa's activity began in 1958, as a geological engineer at the Bucharest Prospecting Enterprise. In 1968 he became a scientific researcher at the Geological Institute of Romania, and since 1993 he had worked at the National Institute of Marine Geology and Geoecology – GeoEcoMar, Bucharest.

In 1970, he completed a one-year specialization internship at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute in the United States. There he studied sediments from the deep part of the Black Sea collected by American expeditions, as well as sediments from the Pacific Ocean (Peru-Chile trench).

He participated in a campaign of the Deep Sea Drilling Project with the Glomar Challenger drilling vessel to study sediments in the northern Indian Ocean, highlighting new aspects in the major accumulation of sediments in the Indus Deep-sea Fan.

Returning to Romania, during many decades of sustained scientific activity he studied geological formations from extremely old, Precambrian, to Cretaceous, Neogene and new Quaternary and present-day deposits and sediments, contributing essentially to the improvement of knowledge of the country.

The first sedimentological researches were carried out in Romania by a group of young geologists, including Dan Jipa, under the guidance of our teachers Academician Gheorghe Murgeanu and professors Dan Patrulius, Vasile Lăzărescu, Ionel Motaș and many others. Sedimentology was the discipline that developed in our country in the 60's of the last century, especially in the atmosphere of preparation for the 5th Congress of the Carpatho-Balkan Geological Association, which took place in 1961 (4 - 19 September), in Romania. It was a scientific event of European dimension and even wider, prepared by the community of Romanian geologists with a special dedication and attention. In preparation for the congress, new studies were undertaken: for the first time, the directions of transport of the constituent material from geological formations widespread in the Romanian Carpathians were mapped - the Albian molasses, represented mainly by the Bucegi Conglomerates, the Paleogene flysch, the Miocene molasses from the Subcarpathians, and others. Dan Jipa was one of the pioneers of the above-mentioned sedimentological research.

On left, Berca, Vulcanii Noroiosi, summer of 2019, photo courtesy of Silviu Radan. On right, January 2020, photos courtesy of Margaret Rutka.

Another particularly important objective of Dan's studies was to investigate the Upper Neogene deposits from the Dacian Basin and to carry out paleo-geographic reconstructions of great interest. The study of Quaternary deposits included both fluvial and marine sedimentation. The studies that targeted the fluvial and sub-aerial deposits focused on the sedimentogenesis of the proximal facies of the Căndești Gravels and the grain-size and morphometry of the sediment load of the Lower Danube. Special attention was paid to the scientific research of loess deposits.

He held the positions of Scientific Secretary (1993 - 1996) at the Romanian Center for Marine Geology and Geoecology, Scientific Director (1996 - 1999) at the National Institute of Marine Geology and Geoecology – GeoEcoMar and was a

permanent member of the Scientific Council of the same GeoEcoMar institute.

Dan Jipa also had teaching activities – at the Faculty of Geology and Geophysics, University of Bucharest, he taught the course on sedimentary systems and facies models for third year students (1996 - 1999) and for master students (2000 - 2002).

Dan Jipa's scientific career is a shining example for many generations of geologists. For his exceptional contribution to the knowledge of the geology of Romania and other regions of the world, he received numerous awards and distinctions. In 2014, Dan Constantin Jipa was elected a corresponding member of the Romanian Academy.

I just want to say that the friendship that bound me to Dan was forged in 1968 when we formed the group of Romanian sedimentologists, and then it strengthened during the 5 decades when we worked together for Romanian Geology. Together with the whole Jipa family, and mainly with Raluca, his daughter, and Liviu, his son-in-law,

I lost a great friend, and the Romanian scientific community a bright figure through the dedication with which he worked in the profession he loved so much.

Dan Constantin Jipa cannot be forgotten! He will always be with us; he will be an example that we will try to follow!
God rest his soul!

Prof Dr Nicolae Panin
Member of the Romanian Academy

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